

A Concise Analysis of the UK Corporate Governance Codes for Institutional Investors

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ABSTRACT

Institutional investors, encompassing entities such as pension funds, hedge funds, and asset managers, are pivotal players in fostering good corporate governance through their significant financial influence. This paper critically examines the challenges and efficacy of institutional investors' participation in corporate governance within the UK framework. It explores the legal and practical difficulties in ensuring their active involvement despite the provisions of various UK Corporate Governance Codes and best practice standards. Key factors such as the agency problem, short-termism, free-rider issues, and conflicts of interest are analyzed in relation to their impact on institutional investors' governance roles. Additionally, the article evaluates the stewardship responsibilities expected of these entities and the barriers impeding their realization. The findings suggest that while institutional investors possess the potential to shape corporate governance positively, structural limitations, fiduciary obligations, and investment strategies hinder their ability to meet the standards set by UK governance principles effectively. This paper underscores the need for a re-evaluation of governance codes to align institutional investors' practices with long-term corporate accountability and performance.

Keywords: Concise Analysis, U.K Corporate Governance Codes and Institutional Investors.

INTRODUCTION

The UK has promulgated several codes for addressing market and financial crises to ensure good corporate governance. Institutional investors are very important aspect of the UK Corporate Governance Codes in ensuring that corporations are managed according to certain defined criteria.

Traditionally Institutional investors comprise of pension funds, investment funds and insurance companies. But the list also includes Alternative Institutional investors such as hedge funds and asset managers. These are capital provided by physical person s, governments or companies to invest on their behalf. The fact that these funds are held in trust for these groups, does create an underlying difficulty in ensuring their participation in Corporate Governance.

This essay seeks to critically examine some of these difficulties of ensuring effective participation of Institutional Investors in Corporate Governance in spite of assured rights through Corporate Governance codes and best practice. It will examine the UK provisions on institutional investors, the powers of institutional investors and best practice and will discuss the main factors that affect the application of the codes of best practice standards to ensure the effective participation of Institutional Investors in Corporate Governance.

It argues that the nature of institutional investors poses some barriers in the smooth applications of UK Corporate Governance principles of regulating corporate behaviour. It concludes that given the general nature of Institutional Investors, the powers available to them and their limitations, it would be difficult for them to actively take up the roles of governance expected of them in the UK Corporate Governance Code.

The essay has divided into four sections. Section one gives an overview of Institutional investors with regards to their nature, trust instruments, delegation and powers. Section two gives an analysis of the UK Corporate Governance Codes informing Institutional Investor practice. Section three provides a discussion on the challenges of implementing the UK corporate governance codes for institutional investors. It also discusses the incentives available to them and the reasons why they do not want to get involved in corporate governance. Section four provides a summary and conclusion. In this essay, the words investors and shareholders would be used interchangeably.

1. Definition of Corporate Governance

Corporate governance has been defined as “the way in which organizations are directed, controlled and led. It defines relationships and the distribution of rights and responsibilities among those who work with and in the organization, determines the rules and procedures through which the organization’s objectives are set, and provides the means of attaining those objectives and monitoring performance. Importantly, it defines where accountability lies throughout the organization.¹The Cadbury Report (1992) identified Corporate Governance as a system by which a company is directed and controlled

2. Nature of Institutional investors

The exact legal forms OF varies widely among institutional investors and covers everything from straightforward profit maximizing joint stock companies to Limited Liability Partnerships (like private equity firms)and they are incorporated by statutes Institutional Investors have been described as having the characteristics of legal entities with the powers and characteristics of a legal person.² These are organizations which pool their resources together to invest in major businesses (like securities, real estate, companies and other assets on behalf of a group of people (clients)³. They vary from joint stock companies to limited liability partnerships and are incorporated by special statutes. They may act independently or form part of a conglomerate.⁴The fact that they are legal persons rather than physical persons has an implication in corporate governance. This is because it creates a link between the income of the ultimate provider and the performance of the company where the fund is invested. The fact that they also differ in forms also suggests that they will also differ in terms of character and level of ownership. As such they have been categorized into three broad categories⁵. These are as follows:

- a) Traditional Institutional Investors: this comprises of pension funds, investment funds and insurance companies.
- b) Alternative Institutional investors: this includes the Hedge Funds, Equity Forms, Exchange Traded Funds (ETF) and Sovereign Wealth Funds
- c) The third category recently included in the UK Stewardship Code is the Asset Managers⁶

These are capital provided by physical person to be invested on their behalf. It could also be pensioning funds from the government or companies on behalf of their employees upon retirement. The bottom line is that these funds are held in trust for these groups of people.

Sometimes, the pension fund trustees delegate the management of their investment to an external body on a contractual basis. This leads to a great competition and puts a lot of pressure on the institutions to perform better than the median fund.

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¹ Code of Good Practice 2011- Corporate Governance in Central Government Departments. http://corporate_governance_good_practice_july2011_pdf. Accessed 03/02/2015

² Financial Market Trends OECD Journal (2014) vol. 2013 N0.2

³A.A Berlie “Property Production and Revolution” [1965] Vol. 65 Columbia Law Review No.1; BS and Black JC Coffee, “Hail Britannia? Institutional Investor Behavior under Limited Regulation” [1994] vol.92 No.7 Michigan Law Review.

⁴Institutional Investors and Ownership engagement, OECD Journal (2014) vol.2013 No. 2 pp94-96. <http://Institutional-investors-ownership-engagement.pdf>.accessed 20/03/2015.

⁵ Ibid at 3

⁶ 2012 UK Stewardship Code.

3.The UK Corporate Governance Codes Informing Institutional Investor Practice:

Institutional investors have become a major force to reckon with in the last three decades in some developed countries especially the UK. They now own more than 60% of the UK quoted shares and as such have become more prominent in the area of corporate governance in the institutions they invest. They stand in a fiduciary position to the people they represent and at the same time have a stewardship duty to the companies they invest in. Sometimes they are caught in-between their representative capacity and their contribution to the investee company. On this note, the UK has promulgated some rules to regulate the relationship between the clients and the investee companies. These codes will be discussed briefly in this section paying greater attention to those codes dealing with institutional participation in corporate governance in the companies they invest.

The role of Institutional investors was given a significant attention in the Cadbury Report of 1992. The report calls on institutional investors to engage in governance. The report states "...given the weight of their shares, the way in which institutional shareholders use their power to influence the standards of corporate governance is of fundamental importance. Their readiness to do this turns on the degree to which they see it as their responsibility as owners and in the interest of those whose money they are investing to bring about changes in companies, when necessary, rather than selling their shares" It has been observed that the institutional shareholders are always quick to sell their shares as they do not engage in long time investment.

While making reference to the Institutional shareholders' Committee on the responsibility of Institutional shareholders in the UK, the Cadbury Report (1992) also encourages the Institutional shareholders to make regular systematic contacts with senior executives so as to exchange views on information on strategy, performance of board members as well as the quality of management in the company. They are also advised to make positive use of rights to vote in general meetings and to take positive interest in the running of the investee company especially in matters relating to the composition of the board of directors.

The institutions are in a position to stay in close touch with the companies in which they invest in a way that is not readily accessible to the individual shareholders. In line with the foregoing, the Cadbury Report of 1992 called upon the institutional investors to ensure that the recommendations in the report were adopted by companies owing to the fact that they are believed to have such influence to ensure the implementation of best practices in the corporations in which they invest. The Greenbury Report (1995)⁷ also states that institutional investors should use their power and influence to ensure the implementation of best practice as set out in the code. Similarly, the Hampel Report⁸ also recognizes the role of institutional investors and their ability to exert influence over the corporations they invest in.

The Myners Report⁹ on Institutional investment concentrated more on the trusteeship aspects of institutional investors and the legal requirement of trustees. The report recommended that institutional investors should be more proactive in taking a stance against corporate underperformance.

The UK Stewardship Code 2012 particularly principle three¹⁰, is to the effect that institutional investors should monitor their investee companies for effectiveness. The code adopts the comply or explain principles (it requires the investors to ensure that the companies comply with the code or explain reasons for its departure from the provisions thereof) It also expects the institutional investors to timely identify issues that could lead to a fall in the company's share price and a subsequent loss of investment. The overall objective of the UK Stewardship Code is to ensure good Corporate Governance by ensuring a better relationship between the institutional investors and the management so as to improve long-term returns to shareholders and the efficient exercise of governance responsibilities.

⁷ Greenbury, Sir Richards (1995) "Director's 'Remuneration'" (Gee &co Ltd, London)

⁸ Hampel, Sir Ronnie, (1997) "Committee on Corporate Governance: Preliminary Report, Gee &co Ltd, London

⁹ Myners, R. (2001), Myners Report on Institutional Investment, HM Treasury, London.

¹⁰ UK Stewardship Code (2012) Principle 3: Financial Reporting Council <http://www.frc.org.uk>. Accessed 20/03/2015

4. Institutional Investors: Powers and Governance Strategy

The power of institutional investors cannot be underestimated given the size of their shareholdings. And the influence they wield in corporate governance can be quite enormous. They could express their dissatisfaction through the voice and exit framework and also through activism. They could either express their dissatisfaction directly to the management of the Investee Company or simply exit by selling their shares¹¹ or public dissent to the management's bid.

Voice: The institutional Investor can either utilize this option either by voting their shares, in the general meeting or extra-ordinary general meeting, through public statement, scoring and rating. The right to vote which is attached to some shares can be regarded as a fundamental element of control by the shareholders.¹² The Cadbury Report (1992) has therefore encouraged Institutional Investors to exercise their right to vote and also disclose their policies on voting. Similarly, Institutional shareholder representatives like the NAPF in the UK have encouraged large shareholders to vote wherever necessary unless they have a good reason not to.¹³

The primary responsibility of the institutions is to their member as such, if they do vote their shares, it must be in the interest of those beneficial owners of the fund with which they invest. The institutions can therefore, vote their shares if they have an inclination that their investee company is about to take an inappropriate line of action that could affect their share value. By using their voice, the shareholders express their dissatisfaction directly to the management. However, the challenge with this option is the cost of responding to the shareholders. Of course, it takes time and energy for the management to fully respond to them.

Exit: shareholders can choose the exit option if they are faced with disappointing situations.¹⁴ This entails selling their shares and investing in another company. This is an escape mechanism. However, the challenge involved in this mechanism is that the shareholders are faced with selling off their shares at lower prices which may be detrimental to them and also affect their clients on whose behalf they invest.

Shareholder activism: This refers to the ability of shareholders to public companies to ensure that management is accountable for their actions. This dates back to the stock market failure of 1929 which was caused by market manipulation and lack of transparency by the directors. The institutional investors have a right to take a public stance against management of their investee company when they have an inclination that the company is about to take inappropriate courses that could be detrimental to their shareholding. For example, in 1996, Farnel Electronics UK made a bid to purchase Premier Industrial Corporation, a USA company for the whopping sum of 1.1 billion pounds. Shareholders publicly dissented on the terms of the bid by issuing a statement about their fear on drop in share value and the probable risk of incurring so much debt.¹⁵

The major aim of shareholder activism is to ensure accountability, transparency and responsibility amongst company directors. This could be achieved through formal and informal dialogue.

5. Critical Evaluation of Institutional Investors active roles in Corporate Governance.

Having discussed the nature and powers of the institutional investors, and the provisions of the UK Corporate Governance Codes and their call for institutional investors to engage with investee companies to help achieve long-term sustainable value, one question that comes to mind is "are investors capable of performing the roles expected of them?" "This section will look at the reasons why it could be difficult for the institutions to perform these roles. It will basically consider the challenges facing the institutional investors in participating in effective corporate governance in their investee companies.

¹¹ A. O Hirschman, *Exit, Voice and Loyalty* (Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts 1970)

¹² C A. Mallin: *Corporate Governance* (2ndedn, Oxford University Press 2007)

¹³ NAPF (1995), UK stewardship Code (2012), principled 6: Financial Reporting council.

<<http://www.frc.org.uk/getattachment>>. accessed 20/04/2015

¹⁴ B Nooteborn, , 'Voice and Exit –based forms of corporate control, *Anglo-American, European and Japanese Journal of Economic Issues* vol. 33 [1999] pp.845-860

¹⁵ C A. Mallin, '*Corporate Governance second edn.*'(Oxford University Press 2007) pp96.

It is quite certain that there is a shift in market and legal powers as a result of the increasing number of institutional investors. With this increase comes the challenges of governance, performance, responsibility and accountability.

6. Agency Problem

One of the major challenges institutional investors encounters is agency problem as a result of long chain or sequence of ownership. For example, a sequence could be in ¹⁶the form where an individual contributes his savings to a pension fund with the aim of investing it for him; the pension fund acting as a trustee, after much advice from an investment consultant, allocates the funds to some fund managers (both internal and external) who distributes the monies or funds to another asset manager. From the illustration, it is obviously a long investment chain and the problem of agency dilemma cannot be avoided.

An essential element of corporate governance is a balanced relationship between the directors and the shareholders. In a relationship between the directors and the institutional shareholders, the directors are the agents and the shareholders are the principals. Sometimes there may arise some problems between the agents and the principals where the agent fails to act in the best interest of the principal. This could be in the area of misuse of power being delegated to the agent or where the agent fails to take appropriate steps in pursuing the principal's interests. In a situation where the agent has more information than the principal, the principal could suffer from information asymmetry thereby resulting to agency costs (the cost resulting from the misuse of positions by the directors and the cost of monitoring and disciplining them to ensure they act in the best interest of the shareholders). These agency problems are more prominent in large corporations where there is a separation of ownership and control. It's been observed that the directors of joint stock companies 'being managers rather of other people's money than of their own, it cannot well be expected that they should watch over it with the same anxious vigilance (as if it were their own)'.¹⁷

One of the reasons of the emphasis of the Cadbury Report on institutional investors as a means of improving corporate governance was because of the size of their shareholding. They have the ability to influence the decisions and actions of the companies. Similarly, the Hampel Report emphasized that the issue of corporate governance would mainly concern the institutions as a result of their large ownership of shares in the companies.¹⁸

The UK governance codes placed more emphasis on the aptness of market solutions and failed to emphasize on the external regulations needed to solve governance problems. They however, place reliance on shareholders to tackle corporate underperformance by taking more active roles in the companies where they have large stakes. Nevertheless, the institutions cannot take active role in governance unless they see themselves as owners of the company rather than seeing themselves as short-term investors. It's been argued that because the most institutional investors see their shares as commodities which do not have any inherent value whatsoever, except that they can be readily sold in active market that the general principle of governance as laid down by the codes could fail. This is because directors cannot be made to give account to shareholders who have refused to take up their legal roles as shareholders.¹⁹

The Cadbury and Hampel Reports both task the institutions to take on the role of the large shareholders with the responsibility of monitoring the company management on behalf of other shareholders. This entails that the institutions should get involved in long term investment rather than their usual short-termism and incurs expenses in intervening to correct management where necessary. On the other hand, having noted that the institutions have a duty to their direct beneficiaries, they need to be free to invest

¹⁶Ben W. Heineman Jr. and Stephen Davis "Are Institutional Investors part of the Problem or part of the Solution?" (Yale School of Management 2011) <<http://www.shareholderforum.com/access/Library/2011930>> accessed 01/05/2015

¹⁷Adam Smith "Wealth of Nations (1776)

¹⁸Sir Ronnie Hampel, 'Committee on Corporate Governance: Preliminary Report (1997) Gee&Co Ltd., London

¹⁹Charkham J.P 'Are Shares just commodities?' in creative Tension?': National Association of Pension Funds, (London 1990) pp.34-42; Helen Short and Kevin Keasey, 'Institutional Shareholders and Corporate Governance in the UK in K. Kensey, S. Thompson and Mike Wright (eds.), Corporate Governance, Accountability, Enterprise and International Comparisons (John Wiley & Sons, LTD 2005).

wherever they desire at any given time without being locked up in any company. This is to enable them find the best possible investment for the funds around in order to fund they hold. On this note, it would be difficult to state categorically that the institution should continue to hold equity positions in troubled corporations and incur further expenses as a result of their intervention in management. This is because there are there are no guarantees that such interventions would be successful as it has been well argued that “the pension funds are not owners, they are investors. They do not want control. They are only interested in making the best possible returns for their client’s money. So they do not have interest in management, all they want is to sell their stock.”²⁰On the other hand they have been described as absentee landlords who do not want to take up responsibility but however make demands of what they feel is their right from management without recognizing the roles they ought to play as owners.²¹

It is trite that shareholders have a legal right to appoint directors whose moral duty is to manage the company in the interest of the shareholders. Whereas, it is not clear what obligations the shareholders owe the company. Every shareholder is faced with the problem of free-riding. So if institution A engages in costly monitoring, while Institution B does nothing, it is obvious Institution A would record lower returns to his clients’/beneficiaries’ detriment. Consequently, Institution A is bound to lose clients. So, to avoid such situations, the institutions develop cold feet in the area of monitoring as it is difficult to see the incentives available to them to take such drastic measures.

7. Incentives available to the institutions:

There are perceived benefits of shareholder activism that more efficient monitoring of company management aligns with the interests of shareholders and those of directors and therefore helps to maximize shareholder’s wealth. Although the institutional investors are encouraged to take an active role in governance, it’s been argued that this approach is not necessarily beneficial to the company for some reasons. First, the institutional investors owe fiduciary duties to their shareholders, not to the companies in which they invest. In some cases, they find that it is in the best interest of their own shareholders to exit rather than vote their shares. Secondly, institutional investors may only be interested in short-term profit maximization and therefore would pressure the investee companies to focus on short-term rather than long-term profits. Finally, the action of the institutional investors may lead to unfavourable media publicity media publicity which results in a fall in share price of the investee company and also a reduction in their investment. In addition, the institutional shareholders may find it costly and difficult to take legal action against the companies such as derivative action as contained in S.260 of the Companies Act and unfair prejudice petition provided under S.994 of Companies Act 2006. The cost of litigation in terms of time and money may make it unattractive for them.

8. Collective action/Free-rider problem:

A company with more than one shareholder is always prone to collective action problems as well as the free-rider problem if monitoring is left to them (the shareholders). The monitoring of a company is a collective good and as such a positive effect arising therefrom is enjoyed by all shareholders regardless of whether they participate or not.²²Hence, a shareholder who behaves in an economically rational way will limit itself from monitoring. The institutional investors may lack the incentive to initiate proceedings against management because of the free-rider problem when other shareholders benefit from their monitoring roles. Therefore, a shareholder would only participate in monitoring if the benefits outweigh the cost.²³

The theory of collective action could be amended to allow for alternative courses of action so as to avoid the free-rider problem. The point of monitoring is that shareholders must be able to gain more than any other course of action but this is however not always the case for institutional investors. The cost of monitoring could be more than the benefit as such it becomes safer for the institutions to abstain from it as it could be at the detriment of their beneficiary²⁴. If the gain outweighs the cost, then it would be

²⁰P.F. Drucker, *The Unseen Revolution; How Pension Fund Socialism came to America*. (Heineman: London 1976) p.82

²¹ W. Hutton, *The State we’re in* (Jonathan Cape: London 1995) p.304

²² G.P Stapledon, *Institutional Shareholders and Corporate Governance* (1996 Clarendon Press).

²³ M. Olsen, “The Logic of Collective Action, Public Goods And The Theory of Groups (2ndEdn., 1971) pp23-24

²⁴ *Ibid* at 11

economically reasonable to get involved but if the cost far outweighs the gains or benefits, it then means it is not in the economic interest of the shareholders as well as their clients to engage in monitoring. An important question here is: how possible is to weigh the gains and the cost before getting involved in monitoring? Since this may be a herculean task for the investors to ascertain, it could be argued that the institutional investors refrain from all measures of monitoring rather than getting into something that the pros and cons could hardly be ascertained.

9. Conflict of Interest

It's been established that institutional investors are more informed to be involved in monitoring than the individual shareholders. However, there is bound to be conflict of interest. For example, where the clients/beneficiaries have divergent interest. Moreover, the institutional investor may have a business relationship with the investee company at one time or the other and as such will be unwilling to be actively involved in governance as it may jeopardize the relationship it has with the company. Therefore, it could be argued that the level of intervention by an institution is directly proportional to the level of relationship it has with the company.²⁵

Furthermore, there could be conflict of interest between the institution and its parent company. As such, any action taken by the institution against management could have a long term negative effect on the company on the challenges of implementing the UK corporate governance codes for institutional investors. It also discusses the incentives available to them and the reasons why they do not want to get involved in corporate governance. Section four provides a summary and conclusion.

10. Issues pertaining to Professionalism and Insider Dealing

Furthermore, it's been established that institutional investors are more sophisticated than the individual shareholders. However, the pension fund managers may lack the requisite training or qualification in corporate governance, finance or investment. Sometimes they do not also have in-house professionals to assist them. Their decisions on investment could be at the detriment of their clients hence they are reluctant in participating in governance. On the other hand, many professional managers are more interested in making money for their clients. They have more concerns over their investment performance than governance.²⁶

If the institutional investors become too involved in governance in problem companies, they may become privy to some sensitive information which has not been disclosed publicly as such, may become insiders and as such could be restricted from dealing with the company's shares as stipulated under the Financial Services and Market Act 2000.

CONCLUSION

This paper has looked at the nature of the Institutional investors, their powers and governance strategies. It has also considered critically, the provisions of the various United Kingdom corporate governance codes with regards to the participation of the institutional investors in corporate governance in their investee companies. However, it could be argued that the attempt to convince the said investors to be more proactive has actually fallen short. The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development in its examination of the contributory causes of the global financial crisis concluded that the institutional investors were not very effective in monitoring their investee companies. Given their nature as trustees and agents of their direct beneficiaries and clients, it becomes difficult for them to also act as stewards to the companies they invest. This is because their motive is only to maximize profit for their beneficiaries through every possible means. As such, they would not want to be locked own in any company.

Furthermore, some investment approaches have made it hard for active participation. This includes inappropriate performances by management and some financial arrangements that promote short-termism,

²⁵ J. Pound, 'Proxy Contests and the Efficiency of Shareholders Oversight' [1988] vol. 20 (1-2) *Journal of Financial Economics*. pp.1218-1223

²⁶ J. Plender, *Going of The Rails: Global Capital and the Crisis of Legitimacy* (John Wiley and Sons publishers, London 2003)

chain of ownership of funds (causing increased conflict of interest amongst owners of funds) portfolio diversification and long and wrong interpretation of fiduciary duties.²⁷

The codes provides that the institutions have the powers to vote their shares if they strongly believe the company is about to take make a decision that would affect their shareholding. Now the question that comes to mind is: do they get the information that the company is about to embark on such course whether appropriate of inappropriate, do they have enough time to consider the pros and cons of the said actions, and if these two questions are in the affirmative, do the fund managers/institutions have the requisite knowledge to understand the skims of the inside directors? It has been observed that the institutions most times are not informed of the happenings in the companies timely. Having to wait for quarterly or yearly reports of which appear unintelligible most times could be too late to take actions. More so, they would not take any action until the Annual General Meeting (AGM) or the Extraordinary General Meeting (EGM) as the case may be may even be detrimental to the investors. Inadequate time to deliberate or consult with their beneficiaries whom they owe a fiduciary duty could also make it difficult for them to vote in general meetings.

It is imperative for shareholders to have sufficient time to prepare for annual general meetings as this is the only chance, they get to obtain information from the company and also express their opinions and ask questions concerning the administration of the investee company. Their ability to participate in the company's general meeting gives them a sense of belonging into the company and helps them to exercise their rights in the company's corporate governance as expected of them in the codes. Institutional shareholders are responsible to the owners of the funds they invest. They have fiduciary relationship with their direct beneficiaries as such must act in their best interest. The institutions have a legal duty to maximize returns upon investment of the funds they hold for their clients. It is also imperative for the chairman to make available clearly formulated agenda for every meeting to enable the institutions make an informed voting decisions without voting blindly.

²⁷ S. C.Y Wong, 'Why Stewardship is proving elusive for institutional investors' (2010) *Butterworths Journal of International Banking and Financial Law* Available at <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1635662> Accessed 15th November 2023